

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BLACKMER****FIRST NAME: GENEVA****COUNTRY: USA****PROGRAM CODE : DIRD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma/Cleenerwerck**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC PAPERS

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is an essential skill to ensure success in all Euclid University courses. There are many facets of academic writing encompassed in the guidelines set forth by EUCLID, some unique to this specific institute. As such, all academic response papers should be developed with the use of the EUCLID Word template as provided by the institution. This template provides an overview of acceptable formatting for this type of academic essay (EUCLID 2015, 6). Other requirements are standardized methods of writing utilized broadly by academic institutions, relating to organizational structure, content, research, revisions, plagiarism, citations, editing, grammar, punctuation, and style consistency.

2) THE FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Academic essays are purposeful in their intent to convey ideas to readers through the presentation of authoritative evidence. As such, academic essays are often persuasive in nature. All academic writing begins with the declaration of a thesis statement. A thesis statement provides an answer to a question framed by the author, summarizing the basis for their argument. This assertion prompts the author to conduct research to support his or her claim. Note-taking is an effective way to evaluate and organize research and will assist in the planning and development of one's essay. Once adequate research has been conducted, the author can begin to draft their essay (EUCLID 2015, 1-5).

a) Essay Organization Structure

The drafting of an essay allows the author to develop the appropriate framework in which they will present their argument. An essay draft establishes the way the question will be answered, the evidence which will be presented, and the overall argument structure. Typically, this structure is ordered as the introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction orients the reader with the topic and introduces the thesis statement. The body portion of the essay consists of several paragraphs and provides the basis for the author's argument. This is where evidence and supporting examples are presented to persuade the reader to accept the author's thesis statement. The conclusion offers a summary of the author's main points and, most importantly, restates the author's thesis. The paper should flow logically and be organized with appropriate headings (EUCLID 2015, 1-5; 40).

b) Providing References

An academic paper is not complete without the insertion of proper references. Each learning institution has a preference regarding the proper format for referencing. Euclid University adheres to the standards of the Turabian style. Turabian style utilizes both in-text citations and footnotes. Euclid University recommends the use of in-text citations for response papers and footnotes for major academic papers. All academic essays should contain a reference list at the end of the paper. Providing sources allows the reader to identify the origin of the information used to validate your argument, and more importantly, avoids the occurrence of plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 33).

c) Avoiding Plagiarism

Plagiarism occurs when an author utilizes an information source and does not provide adequate credit to the author of the original information. This includes failure to quote information, paraphrasing without references, or directly copying and pasting content from the internet. This also applies to submitting papers written by another author under your own name. Plagiarism should be avoided at all costs, not only because it is unethical and unjust, but also because it is a serious academic offense. EUCLID recommends the use of Zotero, a plug-in resource generating citations, in order to maintain consistency in references throughout one's academic career (EUCLID 2015, 9-12).

d) Properly Citing Sources

In order to avoid plagiarism, the author must provide proper citations for sources used, indicating the origin of the information. As previously stated, EUCLID requires citations to be in Turabian style. In this format, parenthetical citations include the author's last name, year of publication, and page number. This type of citation is appropriate when the author's work has been paraphrased in your own words. Footnotes

and reference pages include a full citation, featuring the author's name, year of publication, title of the work, city of publication, and publisher (EUCLID 2015, 34-37). Quotation marks should be used when copying content from a source verbatim, and the original source should be cited directly or parenthetically (EUCLID 2015, 19-24).

e) Grammar, Punctuation, and Style

Euclid University requires students to submit academic papers in English, adhering to standards of writing in either the United States or the United Kingdom. Students should maintain consistency in their writing, adhering to only one of these styles. Major differences include the use punctuation and spelling. For example, the United States requires that punctuation be placed inside quotation marks, while the United Kingdom places the punctuation afterwards. There are also variations in spelling the same word, such as "color" in the U.S., and "colour" in the U.K. Other differences include pronunciation, meaning, and dates (EUCLID 2015, 54-59).

3) CONCLUSION

As demonstrated, proper academic writing is essential to the completion of Euclid University courses, and participation in the academic world at large. EUCLID requires the use of specific university templates, accessed through Microsoft Word, when submitting response papers. EUCLID also requires adherence to universal standards of grammar, punctuation and style consistency, as set forth by the United States and the United Kingdom (EUCLID 2015, 52). The institution mandates that all academic papers follow a proper organizational structure, featuring a thesis statement, introduction, body and conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 1-4). Furthermore, all students should be aware of the consequences of plagiarism, adhering to citation standards of the Turabian style (EUCLID 2015, 12).

As someone who has completed a master's degree in the United States, I am quite familiar with the Turabian style, consequences of plagiarism, and overall standards of academic writing. The information presented in this lesson is practical and universal to all academic papers I have completed throughout my career as a student. Despite my overall familiarity with the academic writing process, Period 1 did offer some new information that is specific to the standards of Euclid University. I was previously unfamiliar with the EUCLID Word templates required for response papers and have never previously submitted academic papers in this format. Additionally, while I am quite familiar with citing in Turabian style, I have never utilized Zotero as a citation resource. I anticipate Zotero to be quite useful as I continue my academic journey at EUCLID, as it seems more efficient at producing citations than the built-in reference features of Microsoft Word.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.